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The Urgency of Indonesian Golden Visa Policy: A Comparative Study

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Abstract

The stabilized economic development can affect the long-term development growth and the implementation of Golden Visa policy is aimed to attract foreign investor to invest that will affect the state and immigration economy. The research method used is qualitative approach to literature review by collecting data from scientific journal, books and legislative product. The result of the research indicates that the implementation of the policies has a positive impact such as elevating the economy growth; meanwhile, the negative impacts are the social conflict and the rise of money laundry. The implementation of Golden Visa policy in several countries to elevate the economy has several differences in condition and provision in terms of the minimal amount of capital to invest, the validity period of the visa and the access gained by individual obtaining Golden Visa. The implementation of Golden Visa in Indonesia as regulated by law is valid for 5-10 years with the variety of minimal investment required depends on the Golden Visa classification. The conclusion of the research is that the implementation of Golden Visa by Indonesian government has several differences with similar policies in other countries.

Keywords: Golden Visa, Economy, Immigration

1. Introduction

Development achievements in Indonesia continue to experience increasingly significant changes that can influence stability through the National Long Term Development Planning 2005-2025. An increase in per capita income has an impact on the stability of the economy in Indonesia, which continues to experience growth. However, from 2019 to 2020, experienced a decline compared to the previous year since 2005, which tended to be stable to a percentage increase of around 5-6%. The decline occurred due to the COVID-19 pandemic, which caused the economy to experience a national recovery process through comprehensive monetary and fiscal policies. The implementation of this policy made economic changes return to stability in 2022. Moreover, the data presented by the Investment Coordinating Board (BKPM) shows that foreign investor investment in Indonesia will reach US\$43 billion in 2022, becoming a historical high compared to 2021 with an increase of 44% (Qolby et al., 2024)

The higher economic growth and increasingly rapid development, especially in globalization and technology, are unavoidable in the era of modernization. The impact of globalization that has made changes to the economy and development is related to the welfare of various countries in the world, including Indonesia. The influence of globalization has a broad impact on various aspects such as economic aspects, aspects of life, and the implementation of economic policies for society (Permana et al., 2023)

The implementation of the Golden Visa policy by various countries aims to attract foreign investors and individuals who are willing to work together to make significant contributions through investment exchange activities and being granted residence permits or changing citizenship. Permission given in the Golden Visa policy to reside in a country to make significant financial investments to increase the country's economic growth. The implementation of the Golden Visa policy is generally used to attract investors, individuals and businesses with large financial capabilities to be able to contribute to the development and economic development of countries that implement this policy (Marsya, 2023).

The implementation of the Golden Visa policy was formalized and ratified based on the legal basis contained in the Regulation of the Minister of Law and Human Rights Number 22 of 2023 containing Visas and Stay Permits and Regulation of the Minister of Finance Number 82 of 2023 which was promulgated on 30 August 2023. Implementation of this policy is aimed to gain profits in the long term, the estimate for the next five to ten years is adjusted to the applicable terms and conditions (Swandana, 2023). Meanwhile, according to the Regulation of the Minister of Law and Human Rights of the Republic of Indonesia Number 29 of 2021 concerning Visas and residence permits, Visa is defined as information presented in writing, either electronically or manually, given by government officials who are authorized individual to travel to Indonesian territory or other countries. Visas contain several related aspects including security aspects prioritizing granting visas intended for foreign citizens, and community service aspects, especially in the best service in immigration (Estheria et al., 2022). Immigration is the frontline guarding the gates in accepting foreign citizens as stated in statutory regulations to provide immigration services, state security and provide welfare for the community (Yepeese, 2023).

The Golden Visa is an offer by the Directorate General of Immigration, Ministry of Law and Human Rights with the concept of providing residence permits for foreign citizens who have influence and can make a significant contribution to the Indonesian state. Implementation of the Golden Visa which is intended for foreign investors by providing a minimum amount of capital investment (Tarigan et al., 2023). This research is supported by previous research by Sarsito et al. (2023) which shows that the implementation of the Golden Visa policy can be used to attract foreign investors in organizing the Indonesian Immigration Expo and Conference by integrating management and collaborative arrangements in a strategic and sustainable manner. Other research conducted by Estheria et al., (2022) resulted in the implementation of visa policy in Indonesia being compared with the implementation of visa policy globally with several other countries which continue to experience changes and transformations adapted to new paradigms to increase economic growth in a country. Apart from that, both negative and positive can be experienced in the implementation of visa policy so that it can provide an opportunity for the country to experience change and development in various aspects. The implementation of the Golden Visa policy is compared with various European and other countries to assess the chances of success and as a suggestion for implementation in Indonesia (Swandana, 2023).

Based on the background stated above, researchers are interested in identifying the urgency of the Golden Visa policy in Indonesia by comparing the implementation of the Golden Visa policy in various countries to improve the economy from the immigration perspective. This research was conducted with the aim of identifying the implementation and impact of the Golden Visa policy in Indonesia.

2. Research Method

This research uses a qualitative approach by examining scientific journals, books, concepts, laws and problems related to the research conducted. The research data source used as legal material is secondary data obtained from literature reviews and empirical reviews relating to the implementation and impact of the Golden Visa policy in Indonesia. The method used in this research uses a literature review approach and carries out reviews tailored to

applicable solutions. Literature review obtained from several sources, namely scientific articles, books, laws related to the economy, Golden Visa policy in Indonesia, as well as immigration and investment. Data analysis was carried out using a descriptive qualitative analysis approach, aimed at analyzing the implementation and impact of the Golden Visa policy in Indonesia, improving the economy from an immigration perspective, and comparing the Golden Visa policy with various countries.

3. Result and Discussion

3.1 The Urgency of Golden Visa Policy in Indonesia

The Golden Visa policy has attracted attention as a mechanism to attract foreign investment and talent, often with the promise of citizenship or permanent residency in exchange for significant financial contributions. Although this policy is often debated in the context of political motives, economic motives tend to be stronger than political considerations in the adoption of the Golden Visa scheme.

Figure 1. Realization of Non-Immigration Tax State Revenue (Trillion IDR, 2020-2023)

Source: Directorate General of Immigration, 2023.

The Directorate General of Immigration, as the determinant of the Golden Visa policy, plays an important role as one of the Ministries/Institutions that contributes to Non-Tax State Revenue (PNBP) through immigration services provided to the community. PNBP realization data shows an increase in immigration services from 2020 to 2023. This increase confirms that the policies implemented by the Directorate General of Immigration have made a significant contribution to supporting national economic recovery. Through more efficient and responsive immigration services, the Directorate General of Immigration is able to attract more foreign investors and entrepreneurs through the Golden Visa, which in turn will help increase investment flows and overall economic growth. Thus, the role of the Directorate General of Immigration in supporting national economic recovery becomes increasingly important and strategic. So, it can be concluded that the policies issued by immigration have an influence in helping national economic recovery.

The decision to implement the Golden Visa policy is predominantly influenced by economic factors rather than political considerations. Surak and Suzuki (2021) highlight that countries that initiate Golden Visa programs often experience economic slowdowns in the years before the policy is announced. This suggests that economic motives, such as the need to stimulate investment and increase growth, play an important role in driving adoption of the Golden Visa scheme. The correlation between Golden Visa applications and economic slowdown underscores the significance of economic motives. Countries experiencing stagnant growth and declining investment use the Golden Visa program as a strategic tool to flow capital into their economies. By attracting wealthy investors and entrepreneurs, these policies can inject much-needed funds into key sectors, stimulate job creation, and stimulate economic activity.

A comparative analysis of countries that have implemented the Golden Visa policy reveals a general trend in which economic necessity dominates its adoption. Countries struggling with economic challenges or seeking to diversify revenue sources often turn to the Golden Visa program as a way to strengthen their fiscal resilience. Moreover,

the spread of Golden Visa schemes across different geopolitical contexts underscores their appeal as a pragmatic response to economic pressures. While political considerations may influence the discourse surrounding the Golden Visa policy, it is the imperative of economic revitalization that fundamentally shapes its adoption. The association between the implementation of the Golden Visa and a pre-existing economic slowdown underscores the instrumental role of economic motives in driving this policy. Prioritizing economic imperatives, countries aim to leverage the Golden Visa scheme as a catalyst for growth, investment and prosperity in an increasingly connected global landscape.

3.2 The Impact of Golden Visa Policy in Indonesia

A Golden Visa is defined as a licensing tool used by foreign nationals to be given the freedom to stay longer. Generally, if you use a business visa, you are only given a period of up to 6 months which must be extended, whereas a Golden Visa can allow you to stay for 5-7 years. Implementation of the Golden Visa policy with the aim of making it easier for foreign investors to obtain residence permits during the process of planting a model in a country using the Golden Visa. Implementation of the Golden Visa policy in Indonesia to increase interest and attract many foreign investors to invest so that it can help encourage economic growth and development in Indonesia. Based on the implementation of the Golden Visa policy in Indonesia, which has had the following negative and positive impacts:

Table 1.3.2: The Impact of Golden Visa Policy in Indonesia

No	Negative Impact of Golden Visa Policy	Positive Impact of Golden Visa Policy
1.	Causing macroeconomic and fiscal risks, for example increasingly rapid economic fluctuations and property waves.	Increasing economic development and development growth in Indonesia due to investment provided by foreign investors in Indonesia.
2.	The influx of investment flows has an impact on the ease of investors in withdrawing investments that have been given to make investments in other countries.	Make it easier for foreign investors to obtain residence permits as long as their investment in Indonesia lasts for a certain period.
3.	Criticism has been aimed at buying and selling citizenship due to the implementation of the Golden Visa policy, which provides annual or long-term residence permits.	Increasing business capital for companies in Indonesia to expand sectors and business networks.
4.	This poses a threat to local MSMEs due to the large number of businesses founded by foreign nationals or investors from foreign countries.	Establishing regional cooperation with various countries to increase economic value through investment.
5.	Increasing money laundering, social conflict and other crimes.	Increasing the availability of employment opportunities and exchanging knowledge.

Based on table 1, by explaining the impact of the Golden Visa policy both negatively and positively in Indonesia from the literature analysis, the research found that the implementation of the Golden Visa policy must consider several things. Even though it can provide economic improvements and other aspects for the Indonesian state, it is important to pay attention to other things that can be considered to provide solutions that could have better potential in implementing the Golden Visa policy. The potential for greater negative impacts to arise is due to the implementation of the Golden Visa policy not being systematic and following developments in the situation globally, regionally and nationally, this is because the Golden Visa policy is dynamic and complex and aims to support and encourage the economy in Indonesia.

3.3 Implementation of the Golden Visa Policy in Various Countries to Improve the Economy from an Immigration Perspective

The role of immigration in foreign investment can encourage a country's economic development. Foreign investment is defined as international capital flows aimed at increasing the reach of company establishments widely. The increase in foreign investment that occurs will provide many benefits, such as foreign investment increasing technological development, knowledge exchange, implementation of the best management systems,

increased household income, competitiveness of local industry, and increased productivity. Opportunities provided by foreign investors to open up export opportunities, boost infrastructure development to support long-term growth, and increase the country's foreign exchange earnings. The presence of foreign companies entering Indonesia can provide a boost to efficiency; strengthen competition in the local market, and innovation that makes consumers feel benefited.

Based on World Bank data, Indonesia is currently ranked 72nd out of 190 countries included in the Ease of Doing Business category. The 2018 report data shows that investment in Indonesia shows that growth identifying foreign direct investment has increased significantly in Indonesia. The following is the implementation of the Golden Visa in various countries and in Indonesia to improve the economy:

Table 2. Implementation of the Golden Visa to Improve the Economy in Various Countries and in Indonesia

Countries	Implementation of the Golden Visa
Portugal	The implementation of the Golden Visa program in Portugal provides investors with several options regarding the investment amount before making a purchase, namely: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The minimum property purchase is €500,000, while the minimum investment made in the financial sector is €1,000,000 or opening a foreign company with the aim of creating jobs. 2. Individuals who have a Golden Visa have access to public services including health care and education in Portugal. 3. The visa validity period is only 1 year but can be extended up to 5 years.
Spain	Implementation of the Golden Visa program in Spain, namely: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Requires investors to invest a minimum of €500,000 in state property. 2. Individual freedom to travel to Schengen countries without requiring an additional visa. 3. The visa validity period is one year and can be extended for two years.
Greece	Implementation of the Golden Visa program in Greece, namely: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Investments made by investors of at least €250,000 in state property. 2. Have the right to freedom of residence in Greece and have access to health care and education. 3. The validity period of the Golden Visa is five years and can be extended every year.
Turkiye	Implementation of the Golden Visa program in Turkiye, namely: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Investments are made by investors worth a minimum of €250,000 in state property, while finances are in banking deposits worth a minimum of €500,000, or opening a business as an opportunity to provide employment opportunities. 2. Individuals who have a visa are given the right to stay long-term in Turkey and the right to live in various popular cities in Turkey. 3. The visa validity period is one year and can be extended every year.
Canada	Implementation of the Golden Visa program in Canada, namely: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. This country does not apply a minimum investment amount given by investors when making a purchase, but the investment purchase amount is expected to create jobs. 2. Have the opportunity to have Canadian citizenship in the future. 3. Initially the visa validity period was temporary, then there was an update that this program was permanent.

Based on a comparison of the implementation of the Golden Visa policy implemented by several countries in Europe, namely Portugal, Spain, Greece, Turkiye and Canada. This policy continues to develop and adopted by several developing countries in the African and Asia Pacific regions with the aim of increasing promotion by attracting investment from foreign investors. The implementation of this program is adjusted to other factors in each country with the aim of increasing economic growth in various countries.

3.3 The Implementation of Golden Visa Policy in Indonesia

According to Minister of Law and Human Rights Regulation Number 22 of 2023, visas and residence permits are granted for longer periods of stay of around 5 to 10 years. The aim of implementing the Golden Visa policy is to improve the economy in Indonesia by making it easier for local companies to attract foreign investors to invest capital in companies in Indonesia. Therefore, in this effort, the Indonesian government provides privileges for

foreign investors who have influence to be granted residence permits to simplify the investment process. The Golden Visa policy, which is implemented as a residence permit or citizenship program, is aimed at individuals who will make large investments for economic growth in a country.

According to article 1 of Law no. 6 of 2011 concerning Immigration, immigration is defined as the movement of people to enter or exit Indonesian Territory and its oversight in order to safeguard and uphold state emergency. Immigration has four functions including state security, law enforcement, immigration services, and facilitating community welfare development. The regulations state that the validity period of a Golden Visa in Indonesia is 10 years if the applicable terms and conditions are met. Indonesia classify the Golden Visa policy in into several categories, one of which is given to figures who have international influence and can provide benefits to Indonesia. The facilities provided by Indonesia for individuals who have a Golden Visa include ease of entry and exit from Indonesia, having access to priority service and inspection facilities at the airport, having the right to stay longer in Indonesia, and having the freedom not to apply for an ITAS (Limited Stay Permit) to the immigration office.

Based on the implementation of the Golden Visa policy in Indonesia according to Minister of Law and Human Rights Regulation Number 22 of 2023, it is stipulated that there are ten types of Golden Visas given to individual investors including global talent, ex-Indonesian diaspora, investors who do not establish a company, investors who establish a company, and digital nomads. According to Article 184, the classification of Golden Visas includes unlimited permits, permanent stay permits, re-entry permits with a certain duration, and limited stay permits. The validity period of the Golden Visa is five to ten years with the condition that the investor makes an investment worth IDR 38 billion for a validity period of five years and IDR. 76 billion for a validity period of 10 years. Meanwhile, investors who want to set up a company must fulfill the requirements by making an investment of IDR 380 billion for five years and IDR 760 billion for 10 years. In addition, investors who do not intend to start a company can make an investment worth IDR 5.3 -13824 for 5 years and IDR 10.6 billion for 10 years.

Table 3. The Types of Golden Visa Indonesia

Type	Implementation of Golden Visa
Former Indonesian Citizens	5-year visa for former Indonesian citizens without guarantor. Proof of immigration bond of at least US\$35,000.
Descendants of Former Indonesian Citizens	10-year visa for descendants of former Indonesian citizens without guarantor. Proof of US\$100,000 immigration bond.
Foreigners With Special Skills	Visa for foreigners with special skills. Requirements include a valid passport, proof of guarantee from the central government or cooperation with state institutions.
World Figures	Visas for world figures with similar conditions, including proof of guarantee from a central government agency or immigration guarantee.
Senior Foreigners	1 year or 5-year visa for senior foreigners. The option with a guarantor requires proof of monthly income of at least US\$3,000, while the option without a guarantor requires a commitment to deposit funds of at least US\$50,000.
Remote Workers	Visa for remote workers. Requirements include a valid passport, proof of immigration coverage with an annual income of at least US\$60,000, proof of living costs, a recent photograph, and a work contract with a company outside Indonesia.
Medical Treatment	Visa for foreigners who wish to undergo treatment in Indonesia. Requirements include proof of insurance, living expenses, recent photograph, and treatment plan documents.

Based on the Golden Visa program, the implementation of the Golden Visa policy in Indonesia aims to attract investors to increase economic growth and development of the country's infrastructure. Apart from that, to collaborate with entrepreneurs in various countries to be able to invest in companies in Indonesia.

4. Conclusion

Based on the implementation and impact of the Golden Visa policy in Indonesia, as follows:

1. The implementation of the Golden Visa policy has negative and positive impacts on the Indonesian state when implementing the program so that anticipatory efforts are needed to overcome social conflicts and can

threaten community welfare, which affects local businesses, but this program has a positive impact on increasing economic growth and infrastructure development.

2. Implementation of the Golden Visa policy compared to various countries with the aim of improving the economy, which is carried out in several European countries such as Portugal, Spain, Greece, Turkiye, and Canada, each of which has minimum provisions for purchasing investments, access is obtained when individuals have Golden Visa, and the validity period of the Golden Visa.
3. Implementation of the Golden Visa in Indonesia, which has different terms and conditions from several European countries, which have 10 types, and various classifications that are adjusted to the investor's goals in deciding to invest in Indonesia.

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